

**STUDENTS' PERCEPTION REGARDING NEWS PAPER READING IN THEIR
CAREER DEVELOPMENT – WITH SPECIAL REFERENCES TO ARTS AND
SCIENCE COLLEGES IN PALAYAMKOTTAI**

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ABSTRACT

Reading provides information and general knowledge and news about a country's economic development. Reading habit not only widens the students' outlook but also enriches their knowledge. This study is undertaken to know the students' viewpoint about newspaper and their utilization towards it. It also exhibits their satisfaction they gained on newspaper and helpfulness of newspaper in their overall development. A well-structured questionnaire was circulated to 90 students. The responses are received from 82 students. After omitting inappropriate responses, 77 responses were taken for analysis. From this study it can be concluded that students must spend more time in reading newspaper. In the Technology ruling world students should make use of this opportunity in a better way. Mobile phones must be used for right purpose and must concentrate on worldly affairs. There should be no hesitation in reading English newspaper. Irrespective of the obstacles they must focus to improve their knowledge to shine in their future.

KEY WORDS: Students' perception, Newspaper reading, motivational factors

INTRODUCTION

Reading is crucial because it fosters kids' imaginations and increases their understanding and empathy. Establishing a reading environment is crucial to helping pupils form a reading habit. Reading habit can be majorly developed through reading newspaper. An example of printed media is a newspaper, which consists of several sheets of printed paper. It includes educational articles about politics, society, movies, education, current events, news, reviews, and advertisements. It offers local, national, and global news. Students reading newspaper will be helpful for them to clear the competitive examination; they will come to know about the job opportunities available. It provides information and general knowledge and news about a country's economic development. Reading habit not only widens the students' outlook but also enriches their knowledge. In fact, the emergence of online newspapers has changed how students look for information, and consequently, the usage of social media has drawn a lot of attention to the use of Internet-enabled devices. The online news have become the inherent part of modern society, it posed a challenge to the print media in some part of the world. This study is undertaken to know the students' view point about newspaper and their

utilization towards it. It also exhibits their satisfaction they gained on newspaper and helpfulness of newspaper in their overall development. In detail it clearly explains the attitude and perception of both printed and online newspaper among Arts and Science college students

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Prof. M.Veerabasavaiah & Amaravathi V (2018) An Attitude towards Newspaper Reading Habits Among Ug And Pg Students Of Bangalore University law college: A case study. In their study they conclude that reading habit, alertness, and knowledge are all enhanced by news paper.

Chetan Sharma Dr., Rajni Saini (2019) **Newspaper Reading Habit Among The Students Of University College Kurukshetra: A Case Study**. Result of the study shows that college students read newspaper for several reasons. They primarily focus on current affairs, carrier, fashion, sports and business. The author concludes from the study that importance of print version of newspaper has not been diminished due to digitization.

Furrakh Abbasa, Muhammad Faisal Faridb, Asif Iqbalc, Sabahat Parveend (2020) **Impact Of Using Newspapers Reading In Improving English Reading Proficiency: A Study Of Pakistani University Students**. The study concludes that the experimental group students showed interest in reading newspapers better than that of control group students. Regular newspaper readers performed better than that of irregular newspaper readers. Most of the students read daily papers to get data and enhance their general information.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the purpose of reading newspaper by the students
2. To know the level of satisfaction attained by the students in reading newspaper
3. To find out the student's frequency level in reading newspaper by the students
4. To identify the most preferred section of newspaper read by the students
5. To investigate the student's mode of preference in reading newspaper

HYPOTHESIS

H01: Opinion regarding the statement on level of satisfaction towards Newspaper Reading are equal to Average level (Average Level=3)

H02: There is no significant difference between male and female with regard to the level of satisfaction towards Newspaper reading

H03: There is no significant difference among Age group with respect to their experience towards newspaper reading.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is an exploratory research where the purpose of this research is to gain a better understanding of the problem or issue, to clarify or define parameters of the problem, or to refine a general idea into a more specific research problem. The sampling technique followed in this study is convenience sampling. A well structured questionnaire was circulated to 90 students. The responses are received from 82 students. After omitting inappropriate

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responses, 77 responses were taken for analysis. This study is purely based on primary data which are collected from the undergraduate and postgraduate students. Primary data are collected directly by the researcher from the original source. In primary data collection the researcher can collect the required data according to his research needs. The tools which are used for analyzing data employed in this study include:

- Simple percentage analysis
- Garrett Ranking method
- Weighted Average method
- T-test
- ◆ One-sample T-test
- ◆ Independent sample T-test
- Anova

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	25	32
	Female	52	68
Age	18- 20	20	26
	20- 23	46	60
	Above 23	11	15
Education	UG	39	51
	PG	38	49
Source of inspiration for reading newspaper	Parents	32	42
	Siblings	4	5
	Friends	3	4
	Teachers	14	18
	Self	24	31
Language Preference	Tamil	57	74
	English	20	26
Frequency level in reading newspaper	Daily	22	29
	Weekly	32	42
	Monthly	7	9
	Occasionally	16	20
Time spent for Reading	1 – 15 mins	39	51
	16 -30 mins	25	33
	31 – 45 mins	11	14
	46 or more	3	2
Place for reading	Home	52	68
	College Library	13	17
	Public Library	9	11
	Hostel	3	4
Most focused part	Whole	29	38
	Headlines only	22	28
	Interested section	26	34

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

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The above table explains that

- ❖ Majority of the respondents are female and belong to the age group of 20 – 23.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are UG students
- ❖ Majority of the respondents agree that their parents are their Source of inspiration for reading newspaper.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents prefer Tamil newspaper.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents say that they read Newspaper weekly due to lack of time.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents agree that they read news paper only for 15 minutes and they prefer home for reading peacefully.

Table 2: FACTORS MOTIVATE TO READ NEWSPAPER

Garrett Ranking method is used to analyze the factors that motivates the respondents to read newspaper

Statement	1 (75)	2 (60)	3 (50)	4 (40)	5 (25)	Total score	Garett Mean Score	Rank
Headlines	51 (3825)	8 (480)	5 (250)	3 (120)	10 (250)	4925	63.96	I
Design	3 (225)	31 (1860)	15 (750)	15 (600)	13 (325)	3760	48.83	III
Layout	3 (225)	10 (600)	30 (1500)	20 (800)	14 (350)	3475	45.13	IV
Picture	8 (600)	20 (1200)	12 (600)	32 (1280)	5 (175)	3855	50.06	II
Well written content	12 (900)	8 (480)	15 (750)	7 (280)	35 (875)	3285	42.66	V

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

INTERPRETATION

The tool used to analyze the factors motivates respondents to read newspaperis **Garrett ranking method**. From the above table it can be concluded that headlines is the most important factor motivates respondents to read newspaper because it shows the overview of the entire news. The second important factor motivates respondents to read newspaper is picture because it induces the readers to read the news. The third important factor motivates respondents to read newspaper is design because the respondents feel comfortable with the process of arranging material on newspaper page

PURPOSE OF READING NEWSPAPER

Weighted Average method is used to analyze the purpose of reading the Newspaper

FACTORS	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	SCORE	AVG. SCORE	RANK
For getting insights	22	22	17	6	13	274	3.56	III
To expand general knowledge depth	13	33	18	10	5	276	3.59	II
For the purpose of education	12	25	28	7	6	264	3.43	V

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For recreation	11	28	25	10	6	268	3.49	IV
To stay up to date	23	22	21	9	7	291	3.78	I
As the day's routine task	5	19	29	15	10	228	2.96	VI

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

INTERPRETATION

From the above table it can be concluded that most important purpose for which respondents are reading newspaper is to stay updated about the happenings of all over the world because it is important for the students to be cognizant with the circumstances. The next important purpose is to broaden the horizon of general knowledge in order to acquire wisdom and to get information. The above mentioned reasons are the most important purpose which persuading the respondents to read the newspaper because the respondents are the students who must be aware of the eventuality around them.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H₀1:Opinion regarding the statement on level of satisfaction towards News paper Reading are equal to Average level (Average Level=3)

Statement	Mean	SD	t value	Pvalue
S1 Value formoney	3.46	1.055	3.770	.001**
S2 Makes moreinteresting	3.35	1.048	2.935	.004**
S3 Makes smarter	3.48	.968	4.356	.001**
S4 Deliverance of content	3.44	1.153	3.361	.001**
S5 Good Guidance	3.68	1.117	5.304	.001**
S6 Passage of time	3.45	1.058	3.770	.001**

Interpretation

One sample t test is used to analyze the respondents' opinion regarding the statement on level of satisfaction towards Newspaper Reading. Since the P value of all the statements are less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. That shows that the opinion regarding these statements is not equal to average level. Based on the mean score it is understood that the opinion regarding all these statements are above the average value 3.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between male and female with regard to the level of satisfaction towards Newspaper reading.

Statement	Male		Female		t value	Pvalue
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
S1- Cost-effectiveness	3.68	.900	2.83	1.264	3.396	.001
S2 – more engaging	3.64	.757	3.21	1.143	1.954	.055
S3 – Intellectual Benefit	3.44	.870	3.50	1.019	.253	.801
S4 – Content Delivery	4.08	.862	3.13	1.155	3.630	.001

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S5 –QualityGuidance	3.84	.850	3.60	1.225	1.014	.314
S6 – Time Well Spent	3.76	.876	3.31	1.112	1.014	.079

Interpretation

Independent sample t test is used to analyze whether there is any significant difference between male and female about the level of satisfaction towards Newspaper reading. Since the P value of the statements cost effectiveness (0.001) and content delivery (0.001) are less than 0.05 therefore the hypothesis is rejected at 1% Level of significance. so there is a significant difference between male and female with regard to the statement value for money and deliverance of content. Based on the mean score it is understood that the male respondents have better satisfaction than the female with regard to the statements cost effectiveness and content delivery. The P values of the statements makes more engaging (0.055), intellectual benefit (0.801), quality guidance (0.314) is more than 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% Level of significance. So there is no significant difference between male and female with regard to the level of satisfaction towards Newspaper reading.

H₀3: There is no significant difference among Age group with respect to their experience towards newspaper reading.

Statement	Agegroupin years			F value	P value
	18-20	21-23	Above23		
Over all Experience Towards newspaperreading	12.80 (3.30)	14.19 (3.54)	14.90 (1.70)	1.816	.170

Interpretation

One way ANOVA is used to analyze the significant difference among Age group with respect to their experience towards newspaper reading. Since the p value is more than 0.05 the hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant difference among Age group with respect to their experience towards newspaper reading. This may be because individuals across different age groups have similar habits, preferences, or access to newspapers, leading to a uniform experience regardless of age.

SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- Students should cultivate a reading habit and read newspapers every day to stay informed and be aware of the events occurring around them.
- It is evident that the entire world is advancing toward technology, and all aspects are becoming digital. Students need to improve their understanding of both print media newspapers and digital media newspapers.
- Focusing on their preferred section in the newspaper is acceptable, but students aiming to pass competitive exams need to concentrate on current affairs.

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- Students ought to dedicate their valuable time to reading newspapers. They ought to set aside specific time for reading the newspaper. The time they invest today in gaining knowledge will place them in a more advantageous position tomorrow.
- It is recommended that universities allocate one hour each week to foster the practice of reading newspapers among students. The library should have sufficient newspapers to promote the habit of reading.

CONCLUSION

Students are a country's future and reading the newspaper can help them become decent citizens who can help their community anytime it is needed. For college students, newspaper reading is essential. Internet is becoming a significant news source for millions of individuals worldwide. People's reading habits are altering as result of how they read news online. The majority of readers in India don't want to pay for subscriptions. Students should be encouraged to subscribe to both the print media news and the online newspaper apps because once they do; they might be persuading to read the newspaper. Due to the value of every dime they may get induced. From this study it can be concluded that students must spend more time in reading newspaper. In the Technology ruling world students should make use of this opportunity in a better way. Mobile phones must be used for right purpose and must concentrate on worldly affairs. There should be no hesitation in reading English newspaper. Irrespective of the obstacles they must focused to improve their knowledge in order to shine in their future.

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